

Large-scale industrial symbiosis of sawmill, bio-refining and side stream utilisation

Pulp mills, paper and/or board mills as well as sawmills of large forest companies, located at the same site or near to each other, create industrial symbioses where the raw materials are procured by a mutual organisation. Sawmill residues are efficiently processed at pulp mills and in bio-energy production. The side streams and waste from pulp production, paper and board mills are bio-refined to value-added products.

A large variety of circular bio-products and bio-materials are manufactured with optimised resources and close-to-zero-waste loops of materials and energy. Local logistics are organized commonly for organising energy, fresh- and waste water, as well as emission management, all driven by the pulp mill for the other companies and production units.

Regional coverage and transferability

Industrial symbioses located around pulp mills are common in Northern Europe. They increase competitiveness, reduce risk and enhance financing possibilities for product and technology development, eco-design, branding, and spin-offs. They are often willing to adopt the regulations and cascading ideas of the circular bio-economy. The symbiosis requires skilled human and economic resources as they are based upon collaboration and trust between companies. This model can be applied across Europe if stakeholders are interested and willing to invest and collaborate into it.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Close integrated production lines with a strategic and functional platform for efficient utilisation of virgin wood and side streams in cascading, recycling and material processes.
- ▶ Mutual business and RDTI collaboration with spin-offs and potential for enhancing the value-added systems within the circular bio-economy and bio-refining.
- ▶ High resource efficiency, surplus of net energy balance, closed loops and minimal material-, liquid- and gaseous wastes.
- ▶ Sawn timber for construction and furnishing uses have long life cycles, low carbon footprints and high re-use potential.
- ▶ Financial safety, investment capacity, economic viability and raw material availability of large industrial consortia.